

Deliverable 2.2.1.1

DATA ON LANDSCAPE AND ENVIRONMENTAL REGULATION
FOR ENERGY PRODUCTION AND INFRASTRUCTURE (VERSION
1, FEBRUARY 2025)

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Data on landscape and environmental regulation for energy production and infrastructure (Version 1, February 2025)

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General Information

Summary

With less than 25 years left before industrialized countries have committed to reaching net-zero emissions, understanding how full decarbonization can be achieved is more important than ever. Across the world, countries are progressing towards this goal, perhaps not yet fast enough, but there is substantial progress nevertheless. This means the technical and political context is evolving and creating new drivers and barriers for continued decarbonization. There is also much policy activity from which we can and should draw experiences for coming policies. Today, these aims are hindered by a lack of data: other than for techno-economic variables, energy policy and political data are scarce, and machine-readable data even more so. In NFDI4Energy, we address this problem.

In the present deliverable, we tackle the challenge of regulatory data for use as empirical constraints in energy modeling or as input variables in policy analysis. We develop time-series datasets on energy infrastructure regulations, specifically rules on where it is allowed and where not to build new energy assets. Here, we focus on renewable energy generation (wind and solar power) and electric vehicle (EV) charging infrastructure regulations. Key aspects include infrastructure *location* regulations (e.g., setback distances) and infrastructure *characteristic* regulations (e.g., noise limits). In this deliverable, we create datasets for four countries – Germany, France, Ireland, and Greece – in a way that the dataset can be expanded to further countries.

We manually gathered the data drawing on primary (e.g., laws, regulations) and secondary data sources (e.g., existing but not machine-readable datasets, published analyses) and verified through semi-structured expert interviews. The interviews helped us verify our data collection of current regulatory frameworks and informed us about expected future policy outlooks and challenges in energy production and infrastructure development. The final dataset holds data on eight types of variables for 1977-2024 on the national level or, when relevant, on the regional level.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

This deliverable is part of Measure 2.2 (Energy policy regulation, political preferences, and logics), with two main deliverables (see below). Moreover, within Task Area 2, we demonstrate using this deliverable with Measure 2.4 Holistic energy system modeling, as discussed later in the report.

- D2.2.1.1 Data on landscape and environmental regulations for energy production and infrastructure (this deliverable)
- D2.2.2.1 Data on policy support
- D2.2.2.2 Data on climate and renewable electricity targets

This deliverable is also related to Task Area 4, where we have developed metadata schema (Measure 4.3 Development of metadata standards for energy research data) and energy policy ontologies (Measure 4.5 Policy ontology; published in other and forthcoming deliverables) – see Figure 1. Moreover, this work provides a data collection framework and template for energy infrastructure regulation, which can help energy modelers/researchers integrate socio-political aspects into the energy system modeling tool/policy analyses.

Related deliverables and measures in NFDI4Energy: D2.2.2.1, D2.2.2.2, Measure 2.4, 4.3, and 4.5.

Figure 1: Links between measures within Task Area 2 and other Task Areas.

Introduction

To achieve the temperature targets of the Paris Agreement, every economic sector must transition to net-zero greenhouse gas emissions. For the energy sector, where plenty of technical solutions exist to this problem, this means a transition to zero emissions as fast as conceivably possible. This is incredibly challenging, both because of the scale of the transition needed and the required speed.

Energy policy-driven research has been essential in supporting policies and driving the transition. For example, energy systems modeling has grown strongly over the last decades. It shows multiple paths for how the energy transition can be successful and how the future energy system can be designed. Across the world, countries have implemented energy and climate policies, to promote technological development, support the deployment of zero-carbon technologies, expand and adapt infrastructures, or reduce emissions. Many of these policies have been successful, but many others have failed to achieve their aims. For upcoming analyses in support of the transition, there is a rich empirical literature from which to draw experiences. However, a key bottleneck for both energy modeling and policy analysis is data availability: especially for social and political aspects, this data is missing, or it is not machine-readable or under the FAIR principles [1], [2], [3], which holds empirical analysis and societally relevant, empirically-based modeling back.

To address this gap and provide data resources to enable politically and societally more helpful and realistic analyses, we have developed time-series datasets of energy policies under NFDI4Energy Measure 2.2 (Energy policy regulation, political preferences, and logics). This includes renewable energy and electric vehicle support policies, decarbonization targets (e.g., carbon emissions and renewable electricity targets), and energy infrastructure regulation. The present deliverable focuses on regulations for where and what energy assets can and cannot be built, particularly renewable energy production (wind and solar power) and EV charging infrastructure. This data is intended to particularly support energy system modeling (by providing actual regulations for use in exclusion masks, etc.) and in policy research (by providing a time series of regulations as input variables for policy analysis); of course, the data is valid and useable by researchers in any discipline.

Examples of energy infrastructure regulations include two main categories: (1) Infrastructure *location* regulation (or *where* we can build what) and (2) Infrastructure *characteristic* regulation (or *what* we can build). For instance, setback distance, one of the key considerations in European renewable energy development, is considered an infrastructure location regulation, while noise limit is regarded as a characteristic regulation. They are two different regulatory points, but they are also related, as noise is one of the factors co-determining the appropriate setback distance.

As it is impossible to drive the energy transition without considering social welfare, energy infrastructure regulation is necessary to handle the trade-offs between environmental impacts and renewable energy potential [4]. Therefore, energy modelers need not only technical and economic parameters but also socio-political factors in the energy system optimization models. For example, Davidson et al. [5] demonstrate the use of our regulatory dataset (the first version of wind regulations in Greece) by integrating it as regulatory constraints into their energy system modeling tool called *atlite* [6]. This tool uses global historical weather data to estimate renewable generation potential, and it is widely utilized in Python for Power System Analysis (PyPSA), a state-of-the-art and open-source Python environment energy system modeling [7], one of which also focuses on an optimization model of the European energy system (PyPSA-Eur) [8].

Much of the data included in our energy infrastructure regulation dataset has been primarily published in a non-machine-readable format, such as in [9], [10], [11], [12]. In fact, machine-readable regulation datasets for wind and solar energy exist, such as the U.S. Solar/Wind Siting Regulation and Zoning Ordinances, published by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) [13], [14]. However, they

do not exist in European countries. This way, our datasets will help energy modelers and researchers can incorporate socio-political data into the energy modeling software and the empirical analyses necessary for progressing in energy decarbonization.

Method

We manually gathered the data from different sources and used various methods. For all variables, we drew on primary (e.g., laws, regulations) and secondary data sources (e.g., existing but not machine-readable datasets, published analyses) to ensure that the dataset is correct and up to date with the latest regulations and to ensure completeness to the extent possible.

In most cases, the regulations for energy infrastructure have not changed much over time: most regulations were introduced at some point and then remained that way. In many cases (except for wind power data), the regulations are less than 10 years old. Some regulation changes we found include, for instance, the setback distance from residential settlements in Bavaria, which has relaxed over time. In October 2022, the state parliament relaxed the 10H rule (defining a setback distance from residential areas as ten times the wind turbine height). The distance between wind turbines and residential areas in forests, near commercial areas, highways, and railway lines was reduced to 1,000 m.

In addition, since the energy infrastructure laws, especially in Germany, contain very detailed information, we did not record all the information presented in the documents, such as the legal summary document from Fachagentur Wind und Solar [11]; we selected only key regulations relevant to energy modelers and researchers. However, we recorded all sources in the dataset so potential users can find all other detailed information from the sources. Also, if concrete laws do not exist but instead focus on individual cases, such as depending on permission for the energy plants to be built, we exclude them from the dataset.

Next, we verified the data through semi-structured expert interviews. The interviews helped us verify our data collection of current regulatory frameworks and informed us about expected future policy outlooks and challenges in energy production and infrastructure development. Consequently, we already know when new regulations are expected, allowing us to update our dataset quickly. In this deliverable, four interviews were conducted in October 2024 and February 2025, as summarized in Table 1.

The data presented in this deliverable holds time series for energy production and infrastructure regulations for Germany, France, Ireland, and Greece in a machine-readable format, with geographical resolution according to the Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics (NUTS) level [13]. The final dataset holds data on eight types of variables for 1977-2024 on the national level or, when relevant, on the regional level.

Table 1 List of expert interviews during the data verification process.

Date	Country	Technology	Organization type	Level of experience
07.10.2024	France	Wind	Renewable energy association	Manager
14.10.2024	Greece	Wind	Wind energy association	Manager
18.10.2024	Ireland	Wind	Wind energy association	Manager
04.02.2025	France	Solar	Renewable energy association	Manager

Note: We could not contact stakeholders in some countries, such as Ireland and Greece, to get feedback on solar data. For Germany, we contacted relevant stakeholders in the solar and wind energy sectors by email, and they provided valuable sources to look for regulation data (none of the interviews were conducted in this case). We primarily relied on the Climate Policy Database (CPDB) [14] for the EV charging infrastructure, and most of the regulations are recent and clear. As a result, we did not conduct interviews for the EV-related data.

We organized semi-structured interviews in three sections, with questions listed below.

- *Section 1: Introduction*
 - o Introducing the NFDI4Energy consortium (who we are and what we are doing).
 - o Explaining the deliverable in Task Area 2 and why we collect socio-political datasets.
 - o Confirming that the interview results will be used anonymously under GDPR.
- *Section 2: Data verification*
 - o Introducing our dataset and asking the experts questions: Are they aligned with your knowledge? Do you have any other regulations or areas in which to add? Have the regulations been changed regularly? Can you tell us about the previous regulations (if any)?
- *Section 3: General discussion (future regulation outlook and challenges)*
 - o Asking the experts about planned regulations and challenges in developing energy production and infrastructure in the country.

Lastly, we improved our dataset based on stakeholder interview results. For example, we noticed some regulations were already outdated; we understood that current laws have been in place in some countries for several years, and the new regulations will be launched in the coming years. All of these were already incorporated into our final dataset.

Dataset

In our dataset, each column’s description is summarized in Table 2. Our dataset is interoperable with other data sources and NFDI infrastructure. For instance, we followed the NUTS level of the European Union and the energy policy ontologies that we are presently developing in NFDI4Energy Task Area 4.5.1 (Development of policy ontology), expected for publication in the fall of 2025, and it is soon to be integrated into the Open Energy Ontology (OEO) platform.

Table 2 List of column entries.

Column name	Description
NUTS	The NUTS level of each country [13]. NUTS 1-3 is possible based on data availability
NUTS_Name	
Country	The country name
Year_decision	The decision year is the year when the responsible authority made the decision to enact the regulation. N/A means we could not find the decision year.
Location_or_characteristics	The main category of the data point <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Infrastructure location regulation (or where we can build what) - Infrastructure characteristic regulation (or what we can build)
Variable	The different types of energy infrastructure regulation variables (see Table 3)
Installation_type	The type of energy assets

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wind power: Onshore, offshore, and all - Solar power: Rooftop, ground-based (including agrivoltaics), floating, and all - EV charging
Installation_scale	<p>The scale (size) of energy assets (only for solar energy)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Residential scale - Commercial scale (including commercial buildings and parking spaces) - Industrial scale - Commercial and industrial scale (The regulation applies to both scales.) - All
Minimum_or_maximum	<p>The indicator shows whether each variable represents each regulation's minimum or maximum value (e.g., minimum setback distance, maximum wind turbine height).</p>
Multiple_conditions_attribute	<p>The condition attribute applies when the regulation has multiple conditions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Group: Each regulation condition applies separately (such as a wind setback distance of 500 m for indoor residential areas and 400 m for residential outdoor areas). - All: All conditions of the regulation apply together (such as conditions of an area of 1,000 m² and a maximum of 1,000 MW are applied together to define a wind exclusion area).
Value	<p>The value of each regulation (if quantifiable). Depending on the conditions, having more than one value for each regulation is possible.</p>
Unit	<p>The unit of each regulation value. The number of units corresponds to VALUE.</p>
Condition	<p>The condition of each regulation (in texts). The number of conditions corresponds to VALUE and UNIT.</p>
Legally_binding	<p>The strictness of the regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Legally binding refers to original laws/policy documents. - Non-legally binding refers to guidelines and expert opinions.
WT_explicitly_mentioned Solar_explicitly_mentioned EV_explicitly_mentioned	<p>This shows whether the regulation explicitly addresses energy assets (wind turbines/solar panels/EV charging). If not, it applies to all construction types.</p>
Source_name	<p>The source of regulation, including the regulation name, ID (such as the law ID), and section (such as the paragraph ID)</p>
Source_ID	
Source_section	
Source_link	
Source_alternative	<p>The links to the original source of the regulation</p>
Text_original	<p>The original text of the regulation. Some relevant sentences were selected for inclusion.</p>
Text_translation	<p>The translation of the regulation (in English)</p>
Miscellaneous	<p>The general remarks of the regulation (if any)</p>
Active_inactive	<p>The status of the regulation, whether it is still active or already inactive</p>

Last_update	The latest month and year the regulation was added or updated in the dataset.
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Table 3 List of regulation variables.

Location or characteristics	Regulation variable	Description
Location	Setback distance	A setback distance is a zoning and spatial planning instrument that sets a minimum distance between objects, such as a wind turbine and a residential building, railroads, transmission lines, and bodies of water.
	Exclusion area	An exclusion area is a zoning and spatial planning regulation that excludes a certain area from being eligible for objects such as wind power plants or cars to be built or entered.
	Priority area	A priority area is a zoning and spatial planning regulation that prioritizes a certain area for building or entering, such as wind power plants or cars.
Characteristic	Noise limit	A noise limit is a zoning and spatial planning regulation that sets a noise limit, such as for wind power plants.
	Shadow flicker limit	A shadow flicker limit is a zoning and spatial planning regulation that sets a shadow flicker ¹ limit, such as for wind power plants.
	Height restriction	A maximum height regulation is a zoning and spatial planning instrument that sets a maximum height for an object like a wind turbine.
Either location or characteristic	Other installation limitation	An installation limitation is a zoning and spatial planning regulation that sets limitation of renewable energy or EV charging infrastructure in addition to height, shadow flicker, and rotor limitations, etc. It can be either by location or characteristics, such as area (lot sizes) limitation, installed capacity limitation, or other setup limitations
	Installation requirement	An installation requirement is a technology standard that sets requirements for the installation of technologies, such as the requirement to build solar PV in new or refurbished buildings.

Note: The variable definitions are adapted from an ongoing task area, Task Area 4.5.1, Development of policy ontology (Last extracted on 17.02.2025).

¹ Shadow flicker is “the effect of the sun (low on the horizon) shining through the rotating blades of a wind turbine, casting a moving shadow.” [15]

Regulations for energy infrastructure

This section briefly summarizes our dataset's key takeaways and implications for renewable energy and EV charging development, focusing on wind and solar power and EV charging infrastructure in Germany, France, Ireland, and Greece.

Wind power

The wind regulations for four countries in our dataset concern only onshore wind power. Table 4 summarizes the wind regulation in four countries by each regulation variable. The blank cells mean no such regulation in a country, as these were verified by the experts. Germany and Greece have national and state (or county for Greece) laws, while Ireland and France have only national laws regulating wind power deployment.

Setback distances and noise limits are highly relevant for wind power development in these four countries, and they are also in line with other studies [4], [12], [16]. This is because it relates to the health, safety, environmental, and aesthetic aspects of wind planning [12]. Focusing on setback distances, all four countries have focused on residential buildings and motorways. These distances vary across countries and can either be in the form of distances in meters or in proportion to wind turbine height. Moreover, each country also enacted other distance regulations. For instance, Germany has more detailed setback distance regulations than other countries, including distance regulations from transmission lines, natural reserves, airports, railways, and military services. France also had regulations regarding distance from coasts, natural parts, and nuclear sites (all these distance regulations were already inactive), while Greece focuses on coasts, world heritage sites, aviation, etc.

Greece and Germany also have additional location regulations, such as exclusion and priority areas. The common exclusion area between the two countries is Natura 2000, a protected nature area [17]. For Germany, it lies also within the responsibility of the states whether wind farms are allowed or not. Natura 2000 guidance is also applicable to France and Ireland since it is a guideline from the European Commission to avoid negative impacts on protected natural areas and habitats [18]. However, we have not found any legal documents from France and Ireland discussing this aspect, and the Irish experts also confirmed that there are no exclusion zones, but building wind farms in the Natura 2000 areas is difficult.

Regarding characteristic regulation, as discussed above, noise limits have shared the most common regulations across countries, ranging from 40-60 dB(A). In some countries, it also depends on day vs. night time or residential vs. rural areas. Lastly, Germany and Ireland also have shadow flicker limits at the same level, 30 hours per year or 30 minutes per day.

Table 4 Recent wind regulation summary in four countries.

Main typology	Regulation variable	Germany	France	Ireland	Greece
Location	Distance from residential buildings (m)	Vary by states	500	4H* (Min. 500 m)	1,000-1,500
	Distance from motorways (m)	National law, but also vary by states	75-100 (Currently inactive)	1H	10,000-20,000 (Vary by counties)
	Distance from transmission lines (m)	Vary by states		23 (only a guideline)	
	Distance from coasts (m)		100 (Currently inactive)		100
	Distance from airports (m)	1000-2000 (national law and in Bremen)			
	Distance from railways (m)	Vary by states			
	Distance from military areas (m)	3000 (only in Bavaria)			
	Distance from others (m)	Depending on conditions, such as natural reserves, radar stations, etc.	Depending on conditions, such as from nuclear installations, natural parts, etc. (Currently inactive)		Depending on conditions, such as from world heritage sites, aviation, etc.
	Exclusion area (Note: Y means it exists)	Y; Natura 2000 areas			Y; Exclusion areas, including Natura 2000 areas
Priority area (Note: Y means it exists)	Y; Wind priority areas			Y; Wind priority areas	
Characteristics	Noise limits (dB(A) or dB)	40-60 dB(A) (depending on day/night time and residential/rural areas)	35 dB(A)	43-45 dB(A) (depending on day/night time)	45 dB

	Shadow flicker limits (h/year or min/day)	30 or 30		30 or 30	
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*Four times of wind turbine height

Solar power

For solar power, Table 5 summarizes the solar regulations in four countries. Compared to wind power, solar regulations are more complicated as they concern both types of installation (ground-based solar and rooftop solar) and installation scales (residential, commercial, industrial, etc.). Solar power has a few setback distances (such as roof-related setback distances for efficiency/safety reasons [19]). At the same time, installation limitations and requirements are more common infrastructure regulations across countries due to technological development and standards. Most regulations are at the national level. Only Germany and Greece have state/county-level regulations. The blank cells in the table mean we are unsure whether the regulations are available.

Considering the ground-based solar systems, only Greece and Germany have setback regulations. For example, Germany has a setback distance for ground-based PV from the motorway of 40 m, while Greece set distance rules of 100-150 m from the coast and other special environmental areas.

Moreover, Germany and Greece have exclusion area regulations (including floating solar only for Greece), while France has set some priority zones for ground-based solar systems. France and Ireland also have installation limitations and requirement regulations for ground-based solar panels, such as total installation area limitations for installing ground-based solar systems or agrivoltaics (especially for France). In addition, Ireland is the only of the four countries with a solar installation height regulation, in this case, of a maximum of 2-2.5 m.

Ireland has more regulation types regarding rooftop solar than other countries, such as rules regarding roof-related distances, exclusion areas, installation height, and other installation limitations. Germany has both installation limitations and requirements at the national and state levels, while France has only installation requirements at the national level. Lastly, we have not found any regulations for rooftop solar systems in Greece.

Table 5 Recent solar regulation summary in four countries.

(a) Ground-based solar

Main typology	Regulation variable	Germany	France	Ireland	Greece
Location	Distance from the coast (m)				100
	Distance from others (m)				100-150 (referring to special environmental certificate projects, including Natura 2000)
	Distance from motorway (m)	40			
	Exclusion area (Note: Y means it exists)	Y; Natura 2000 areas			Y; Exclusion areas, including Natura 2000 areas, are also applicable to floating solar systems
	Priority area (Note: Y means it exists)		Y; Priority areas		
	Other installation limitation		Percentage of total area limitation for agricultural PV that can no longer be exploitable after installations	Total installation area limitation (such as 50 m ²) for a specific site depending on the installed capacity	Total installation area limitation (such as maximum area for solar installations that allow cover in public areas)
	Installation requirement			Open space requirement after PV installations (such as 25 m ² required for private open space)	

Characteristics	Solar height (m)			2-2.5	
	Installation requirement		Agricultural yield requirement in the same land area, compared to without agricultural PV installations		

(b) Rooftop solar

Main typology	Regulation variable	Germany	France	Ireland	Greece
Location	Distance related to the roof (cm)			15-200 (depending on conditions such as the distance between the roof edge and the panels)	
	Exclusion area (Note: Y means it exists)			Exclusion areas	
	Other installation limitation	Total roof area limitation that can be used to install PV systems (Vary by states)		Total roof area limitation that can be used to install PV systems	
	Installation requirement	Roof area/parking space required to install rooftop solar (Vary by states)	Percentage of roof area required to install rooftop solar		
Characteristics	Solar height (m)			1.6	

	Other installation limitation	Installed capacity limitation (Vary by states)			
	Installation requirement	Installed capacity required to install rooftop solar (Vary by states)			

EV charging infrastructure

Since EV technology is relatively new compared to wind and solar power, we have found limited and recent legislative documents for EV charging infrastructure regulation (See Table 6). The blank cells in the table mean we are unsure whether the regulations are available.

Before 2020, Greece mainly legalized EV charging stations and allowed gas stations to install them. After that, the countries started to set some requirements, such as the percentage or number of EV charging stations required in parking lots and buildings, like the other three countries. Moreover, the EU passed a new law requiring EV charging stations every 60 km along highways [19]. As a result, all countries except Greece have already incorporated it into their national laws.

Table 6 Recent EV charging infrastructure regulation summary in four countries.

Main typology	Regulation variable	Germany	France	Ireland	Greece
Location	Distance between EV charging stations along highways (m)	60	60	60-120	
Characteristics	Installation requirement	Percentage or number of EV charging station requirements Installed capacity requirements for EV charging stations	Percentage or number of EV charging station requirements Installed capacity requirements for EV charging stations	Percentage or number of EV charging station requirements Installed capacity requirements for EV charging stations	Percentage or number of EV charging station requirements

Remarks and Future Works

Remarks

Correctness and completeness of data

We have done everything we can to ensure the accuracy and completeness of our dataset, including multiple review rounds with several FAU STP group members. Yet, we cannot guarantee that all information is correct and complete. It is, to the best of our knowledge. Not all data points are readily available; although we cite them correctly, documents may hold incorrect data. In some cases, interpreting regulations is a non-trivial task, especially in different languages, and we do not always know each country's energy-political context and tradition. We refuse any liability for any errors or inaccuracies.

Source of data

This dataset came from desk research and expert interviews. The source columns include links or references to the specific regulation of each row. All source links in our dataset are live as of February 2025.

Future works

We plan to collect data for further countries, such as other European countries, and keep updating our existing regulation dataset.

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